

New Space ESD-Resistant Smart-Antistatic Wires and Cables insulations

Pierre-Yves Mikuš, Stéphanie Huguenot, Gérard Biscaras

Axon Cable SAS, 2 Route de Châlons en Champagne, 51210 Montmirail, France

Abstract— Space is a harsh environment and especially for polymers materials which can be exposed to ionizing and ultraviolet radiations, atomic oxygen (ATOX), wide temperature cycling and electrostatic discharges (ESD) issues. Axon’ with its development and manufacturing solutions in all fields of electrical interconnect, has been exploring and developing various new and innovative products to provide the best performance and optimized mass saving solutions to meet all Space requirements. This paper presents some latest results concerning the development of new materials and antistatic wires and cables solutions with controlled insulation volume resistivities in the range of 10^7 to 10^{15} ohm.cm to prevent surface and internal electrostatic discharge (ESD).

I. INTRODUCTION

A. ESD risk in Space for Wires and Cables

Wires and cables used in Space are susceptible to initiating electrostatic discharges (ESD) under certain conditions. These ESD phenomena are mainly caused by the use of excellent electrical material insulation layers and their ability to store and build-up electrostatic charges due to their intrinsic high resistivity [1].

The incoming charged particles can build-up inside dielectrics up to “break down” threshold levels, leading to electrical arcs discharged into nearby sensitive circuits (Fig 1).

The approximate regions of concern for internal charging issues (iESD) are illustrated in Fig 2. ESD phenomena can lead to catastrophic failures such as occurred on ADEOS-II in 2003 which resulted in the complete loss of the satellite [2].

Fig 1. Example of arc damage sustained on a solar array (ESA EURECA)[3]

Fig 2. Earth regimes of concern for on-orbit internal charging hazards for spacecraft with circular orbits[4]

II. INNOVATIVE ANTISTATIC WIRES CONCEPT

A standard way to protect electrical harnesses and other ESD sensitive components is to cover them with conductive films, braids or coatings in order to quickly absorb and evacuate most of the incoming charged particles towards the mass of the satellite. The drawback of this solution is the increase in mass, cost and volume of the interconnect solution, and its reduced flexibility. The thickness of any additional conductive material also needs to be optimized in order to reduce the residual radiation flux low enough to fully prevent any internal ESD (iESD) risk. This conductive surface layer require also a specific grounding, which further increase the mass, cost and complexity of the systems.

An innovative approach explored by Axon’ to reduce the ESD risk for wires and cables without these drawbacks is to fully replace all the highly insulating dielectrics with “leaky” materials in order to permit a fast enough evacuation of incoming charged particles to the nearest conductive layer. The main objective of this development, supported by ESA activity ITT AO/1-7877/14/NL/RA, was to explore this concept by formulating, processing and testing new wire and cable insulation materials able to dissipate through the central conductor the electrostatic charges that build up in a Space environment.

The main challenge was to formulate and process new materials with volume resistivities low enough to permit sufficient charge decay speed (to ensure Space-ESD resistance), but at the same time maintaining sufficiently high resistivity values to guarantee the electrical insulation

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performance of the finished wires (acceptable insulation resistance and dielectric strength).

A. Maximum Bulk Resistivity target for ESD-safe insulations

Standard and qualified wire and used in Space are built from excellent electrical polymers insulations exhibiting volume resistivities in the range of 10^{16} to 10^{21} ohm.cm. A safe material bulk resistivity value to prevent insulation charge build-up in Space is a function of the worst case radiation scenario considered (current density passing through the insulation), insulation thickness, and the maximum acceptable voltage increase inside the dielectric (dielectric strength). The ESA Spacecraft charging standard[5] indicates that for dielectric materials laid on top of a more conductive material, the resistivity of the dielectric shall be such that the electric field anywhere within the dielectric does not exceed an E_{MAX} value. This would be fulfilled through the requirement that the resistivity (r) is less or equal to the ratio of E_{MAX} over the current density J (Eq. 1)

$$r \leq \frac{E_{MAX}}{J} \quad (1)$$

In a similar way, NASA and JAXA Space charging standards guidelines also define some typical worst case scenarios and maximum bulk resistivity values in order to prevent unacceptable charging risk[4-6]. A maximum acceptable volume resistivity value to ensure Space-ESD insulation safety would then be mainly between 10^{11} to 10^{14} ohm.cm based on reviewed references and their associated worst-case charging rate hypotheses.

It should be noted that insulation materials exhibit also different radiation-induced conductivity (RIC) behaviour, which corresponds to an increase in insulation conductivity (decrease of volume resistivity) as a function of the radiation spectra[7, 8]. For materials with high bulk resistivity ($\geq 10^{16}$ ohm.cm) or long polarization decay times, the electrical measurement method used (electrometer at constant voltage, charge storage decay, etc..) has also an important influence on measured resistivities[9, 10].

B. New Antistatic Wire prototypes results

New modified ETFE-based antistatic formulations and coated AWG24 silver-plated copper wire prototypes (finished diameter ≈ 1 mm) have been successfully manufactured and characterized. A summary of achieved volume resistivities range for these new materials and cables prototypes compared to ESA ECSS-E-ST-20-06C and NASA JSC-66552 electrical classification of insulations is presented in Fig 3.

Electrical classification of insulations based on their volume resistivities

Note: "Antistatic" as defined in the ESD Glossary of Terms refers to the ability of a material to inhibit triboelectric charging and is not necessary correlated to its resistivity

Fig 3. Summary of new modified ETFE-based materials and insulated wires developed through ESA project ITT AO/1-7877/14/NL/RA, as a function of their volume resistivity. Insulation classification based on ESA and NASA ESD-charging standards [5, 11]

The new developed solutions exhibit volume resistivities in the range of $\approx 10^7$ to 10^{15} ohm.cm compared to $\geq 10^{17}$ ohm.cm for witness ETFE materials and insulated wires. Measured resistivities vary as function of applied voltage, material formulations, processing methods and parameters used.

Three references of these newly developed antistatic coated wire prototypes have been selected for further electrical, mechanical and thermal characterizations based on ESA ESCC 3901 requirements (generic Space specification for low voltage wires and cables). These include spark test, voltage test, abrasion resistance, cut-through resistance, blocking, shrinkage, cold bend test and thermal accelerated ageing. Complementary tests have also been performed during the development stage, such as tensile properties of the modified insulations, breakdown voltage, dielectric strength and volume resistivity measurements at high and low temperature, and as a function of applied voltage and duration.

The Table 1 presents an extract overview of some test results for one selected antistatic wire prototype intended for low voltage applications ($\leq 100V$). It was possible to achieve antistatic coated wires with very thin insulations thickness ($\leq 250\mu m$) whilst still maintaining a good balance of electrical and mechanical performance. The influence of temperature cycling on the electrical properties of these new materials has also been investigated : it can be seen, for example, that the antistatic material formulation W401B1 with a measured volume resistivity of 10^{10} - 10^{11} ohm.cm at 500Vdc remains stable throughout the whole tested temperature range (-60 to +160°C, Fig 4).

Another interesting result is the influence of applied differential voltage on the measured wire insulation resistivity. At low voltage stresses, below a critical level (≈ 100 - $250V$, depending on the wire reference), the coated wire maintain a high electrical resistance with measured volume resistivities in the range of 10^{11} – 10^{15} ohm.cm. The measured resistivity decrease as the applied voltage rises, and enter the “antistatic range” when the differential voltage increases beyond a critical value. At these higher voltage levels, measured volume resistivities drop between [10^7 – 10^{11}] ohm.cm depending on the coated wire reference, the material formulation and the cable manufacturing tooling and processing parameters used. An illustration of this dynamic “smart antistatic” behaviour is presented in Fig 5 for the W4825M1 wire prototype.

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Fig 4. Volume resistivity as function of temperature for an antistatic molded disk specimen W401B1 and measured at 500Vdc. Colored insulation classification range as per ESA and NASA ESD-charging standards [5, 11]

Table 1: Evaluation test plan results extract for the W4825M1 antistatic wire prototype

Wire Prototype reference : W4825M1			
Conductor	Type	SPC AWG 24	
	Diameter	Ø 0.64mm	
Wire Insulation system	Insulation material	Modified Antistatic ETFE	
	Finished wire Ø (mm)	≈ 1.10 mm	
Spark Test	ESCC 3901 style	Max Voltage	800V - PASS
Voltage Test	ESCC 3901 style	Max Voltage	500V - PASS
Abrasion	ESCC 3901/012 requirements	Minimum 100 cycles	>2000 cycles
Cut-through		Mini 40 N	>150 N
Blocking		200°C - no sticking	PASS
Shrinkage		Max 2mm	< 0.120 mm
Tensile Properties	No standard specification	Stress at break (MPa)	>35MPa
		Strain at break (%)	>250%
Insulation bulk resistivity	Volume resistivity (ohm.cm) Based on ASTM D257 DC voltage after 60sec	at 10V	2.4E+15
		at 50V	1.0E+15
		at 100V	8.3E+14
		at 200V	1.3E+13
		at 300V	1.8E+11
Cold Bend Test -80°C 4hours	Initial volume resistivity (ohm.cm)	at 10V	5.7E+14
		at 50V	2.0E+13
		at 250V	5.2E+11
	after Cold bend (ohm.cm)	at 10V	3.0E+13
		at 50V	2.1E+12
		at 250V	1.9E+10
Final Voltage Test	at 250V	PASS	
Accelerated thermal ageing +230°C 120hours	Initial volume resistivity (ohm.cm)	at 10V	2.5E+15
		at 50V	1.5E+15
		at 250V	2.4E+12
	After Thermal ageing (ohm.cm)	at 10V	3.1E+12
		at 50V	7.7E+10
		at 250V	1.5E+08
Final Voltage Test	at 250V	PASS	

This electrical behaviour could be of special interest for Space applications where bus voltages of many spacecraft power sub-systems are usually in the 28V – 100V range. In such cases, and at operational voltages, these new “smart-

antistatic” coated wires would still exhibit good insulating performances, and in case of a voltage anomaly (due to deep dielectric charging for example), the special modified insulation would allow a smooth decay of the charges through the central conductor. This would prevent voltage rising inside the dielectric, and therefore avoid any ESD events such as arcing and subsequent electrical breakdown of the insulation.

III. CONCLUSION

New Axon’ “smart-antistatic” wires prototypes with variable volume resistivities and for different operational voltage applications are now available to the Space community.

Next steps toward a full Space ESCC-type qualification of these new antistatic cables and materials would be the investigation of their RIC parameters and charge decay behaviour when exposed to a GEO-like radiation spectra, in vacuum and thermal cycling between -150 to +150°C. This would help to confirm the effective Space-ESD resistance of this innovative solution, and to optimize if required wires designs and material formulation.

Fig 5. Volume resistivity measurement on the new antistatic modified ETFE wire prototype W4825M1 as function of applied voltage (dc) and testing time duration.

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